

LINGUISTICS IN THE MODERN WORLD

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Abstract: the article describes the current state of Russian linguistics, describes its main directions.

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The popular opinion about linguistics and linguists gives the bulk of people an idea of it as a science aimed at compiling textbooks and manuals on the Russian language, establishing the norms of correct pronunciation, and in the ranks of the especially ignorant, linguists are translators or just people who speak several languages other than their own native.

Of course, such an idea has nothing to do with what this science really is. The versatility and interrelation of linguistics with other sciences makes it possible to look at it as knowledge that penetrates into all spheres of human activity just because the subject of its study can be found everywhere.

Classifying the sections of linguistics, there are several main directions, which will be discussed in this article:

- 1). Cognitive Linguistics;
- 2). Corpus linguistics;
- 3). Computational linguistics;
- 4). Discoursology;
- 5). Sociolinguistics.

The branch of linguistics bordering on psychology and called cognitive linguistics studies the connections between human consciousness and language. Cognitive scientists are specialists who study language and speech as a means of

forming certain concepts, certain categories and concepts that reflect the role of language in the study and cognition of the surrounding world and events by a person. This direction allows you to see the reflection of life experience in the environment of linguistics.

According to the hypothesis of linguistic relativity associated with the names of E. Sapir and B. Whorf, the structure of language determines thinking, however, experts in this field continue to study the question of the degree of influence of language and consciousness on each other and this topic has occupied science for quite a long time.

One of the most interesting and relatively recent discoveries in this field is the application of the achievements of cognitive scientists in the field of analysis of literary texts, called cognitive poetics.

The essence of corpus linguistics is clear from its own name, however, it is worth clarifying the meaning of the corpora that are the subject of its study. In this context, the term "corpus" means a formed layer of linguistic knowledge designed to solve certain problems of linguistics, possessing such indispensable qualities as typewritten font and the integrity of the essence, subordinate to the structure and classified in a certain order. Such corpora include ordered sets of texts united by common features – genre, author, language, belonging to a certain historical period, and so on.

This science originated in the 60s of the twentieth century in the USA and is quite young. In Russia, it received an impetus to appear a little later – in the 80s. One of the most developing corpora is the National Corpus of the Russian Language – NKRYA, which includes many subsections.

With the development of computer technology in the late twentieth and early twenty-first centuries, computational linguistics became widespread. This direction combines all the important aspects of linguistics, united by the use of software and computer technology. The purpose of this section of linguistics is the automated analysis of the language necessary for the formation of a behavior model and its

work in various situations, areas and spheres. One of the vectors of action of this science is the improvement of machine translation, transcription, information retrieval, development and creation of programs and widgets related to the use of language. A striking example of the result of such developments is the T9 dictionary. Another direction in linguistics that can be attributed to the new and the youngest is discoursology. Experts interpret this concept as speech immersed in life. It can be understood as the totality of all speech and facial expressions, gestural and rhythmic signs, experience and worldview of participants in the language process.

The study of discourse is a separate field of knowledge that attracts specialists from various scientific blocks, such as psychology, ethnography, sociology, philosophy, cultural studies and even stylistics. Such a multi-sided analysis allows us to draw conclusions about the meaning of speech and its work in various life situations and link this result with psychological and social factors.

The relationship between language and the social sphere is the subject of analysis of sociolinguistics. One of the most striking examples of such specialists in literature is Henry Higgins in the play *Pygmalion*. The professional ability of this hero was to determine the origin of a native speaker by his dialectical pronunciation. Scientists engaged in research in this field also analyze national languages, social differences and features of multilingualism and social roles. This includes the study of slang, including one of the most common in the modern world, the language of the "Internet" and much more. Sociolinguistics is growing and actively developing. The most pressing problems of our time in this area are the extinction of dialects and feminities.

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